

Boundary control of a heat equation

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Received: 08 Jan 2021

Accepted: 29 Jan 2021

Published Online: 27 Apr 2021

Abstract: In this paper, we will study practical problems of optimal control governed by differential equations with partial derivatives. In the framework of this work, we will deal with an optimal control problem applied to the heat equation. This problem has many applications in the field of physics and in automation.

Key words: Partial differential equations, approximate solutions, optimal control.

1. Control theory and difference method

1.1. Introduction

In mathematics and engineering, the purpose of control theory is to study the behavior of parameterized dynamic systems as a function of the trajectories of their parameters. Of note is the following work related to exact or approximate controllability of ordinary and fractional differential equations : The work of I. Rezzoug et al. on the controllability theory [[1], [12], [13], [3], [11], [15], [16], [14], [19]] ; As well as the research of V. Vijayakumar and R. Udhayakumar on the theory of controllability and approximate controllability of fractional differential equations [[7, 18, 20, 21, 23, 24]].

We place ourselves in a set, the state space E on which we define a dynamic. The course of time is modeled by an integer $k \in \mathbb{Z}$. The dynamics of the state of the system $(x_k)_{k \in \mathbb{Z}}$ only depends on the state of the system in the previous state and on the value of an exogenous parameter (the control parameter) denoted by u and which takes its values in a set \mathcal{U} .

The dynamics of the system is then totally defined by a function

$$f : E \times \mathcal{U} \times \mathbb{Z} \mapsto E,$$

and a starting point $e \in E$; it is written :

$$x_{k+1} = f(x_k, u_k, k), x_0 = e, u_k \in \mathcal{U}, k \in \mathbb{Z}. \quad (1)$$

The main question of control theory is : what is the behavior of x according to that of u ?, for example can we choose a sequence of controls u_1, \dots, u_N such that x_N is worth x^* , a target value chosen elsewhere ?.

The system (1) which is discrete (time takes only integer values) has a continuous equivalent (time flows continuously), which we can write :

$$x' = g(x(t), u(t), t), x(0) = e, u(t) \in \mathcal{U}, t \in \mathbb{R}. \quad (2)$$

In this context x' is the temporal derivative of x at time t , it is therefore necessary to provide E with a structure giving access to the derivation (for example a structure of normalized vector space).

As examples : driving a car is a dynamically controlled system : control is the angle of the steering wheel, the pressures exerted on the brake and the accelerator, and the state is the position of the car on the road.

The game of tennis is a dynamic controlled system : control is my position on the court and the position and movement of my racquet, and the condition is the position of the ball.

Piloting a torpedo is also a dynamically controlled system : control is the position of its fins, and status is the position of the torpedo.

These examples show that the objective of the control is qualitatively quite natural. For example, for a car, it is about staying on the road or winning a race, for tennis to send the ball back onto the court, and for the torpedo to sink a moving ship.

In this work, we are interested in the application of the finite difference method to solve an optimal control problem applied to the heat equation.

We organized the presentation of this work as follows:

In the first section, we recall some properties on the control theory, and the finite difference method to solve a problem of the linear heat equation.

The second section is devoted to solving a practical problem in optimal control of the heat equation with a control at the edge of the domain.

Finally, we end this work with a conclusion, as well as some references.

1.2. Control theory

1.2.1. Presentation of the problem

The aim of this paragraph is to solve an optimal control problem applied to the heat equation. This resolution is located in an open bounded Ω domain of \mathbb{R}^n with mixed conditions of Dirichlet and Neumann at the edge of this domain, noted $\partial\Omega = \Gamma_d \cup \Gamma_n$.

The problem to be solved is the following stationary heat equation :

$$\begin{cases} -\Delta y &= 0 & \text{in } \Omega. \\ y &= 0 & \text{on } \Gamma_d. \\ \frac{\partial y}{\partial n} &= u & \text{on } \Gamma_n, \end{cases}$$

with $y = y(u)$ and $u = u(x)$, where y denotes the temperature and u the control.

Our but is then to find the temperature y such that it is equal to a given temperature y_0 , or at least very close to it.

A standard choice of the following cost functional J :

$$J(u) = \frac{1}{2} \int_{\Omega} |y(u) - y_0|^2 dx + \frac{\varepsilon}{2} \int_{\Gamma_n} u^2 dx,$$

ε represents the efficiencies-cost compromise.

We define the cost functional J because it gives good solutions approximated numerically. By comparison with the direct calculation of reference.

We are interested in the following optimal control problem :

$$\min J(u) \quad \text{such as } u \in L^2(\Gamma_n).$$

The problem then comes down to finding $y \in H_0^1(\Gamma_d)$ such that $\forall v \in H_0^1(\Gamma_d)$,

$$\int_{\Omega} -\Delta y v = 0,$$

by Green's formula we have :

$$\int_{\Omega} \nabla y \nabla v - \int_{\Gamma_n} \frac{\partial y}{\partial n} v = 0,$$

we then arrive at the following varitional formulation :

$$\int_{\Omega} \nabla y \nabla v = \int_{\Gamma_n} uv,$$

we have $V_h \subset H_0^1(\Gamma_d)$ of finite dimension.

We assume the finite dimensional problem and in the following, we will continue to denote by V and H the finite dimensional subspaces of $H_0^1(\Gamma_d)$ and $L^2(\Gamma_n)$.

To minimize the functional J , we must first perform the derivation operation on it. For this, we introduce the derivative of Gâteaux, defined as follows :

$$J'(u, h) = \lim_{t \rightarrow 0} \frac{J(u + th) - J(u)}{t}.$$

Let's start by calculating $J(u + th)$:

$$J(u + th) = \frac{1}{2} \int_{\Omega} |y(u + th) - y_0|^2 dx + \frac{\varepsilon}{2} \int_{\Gamma_n} (u + th)^2 dx.$$

Since $u \rightarrow y(u)$ is linear, we have : $J(u + th) = J(u) + ty(h)$.

So we have.

$$\begin{aligned} J(u + th) &= \frac{1}{2} \int_{\Omega} |(J(u) + ty(h)) - y_0|^2 dx + \frac{\varepsilon}{2} \int_{\Gamma_n} (u^2 + t^2 h^2 + 2thu) dx \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \int_{\Omega} (|y(u) - y_0|^2 + t^2 |y(h)|^2 + 2t(y(u) - y_0)u(h)) dx \\ &\quad + \frac{\varepsilon}{2} \int_{\Gamma_n} (u^2 + t^2 h^2 + 2thu) dx \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \int_{\Omega} |y(u) - y_0|^2 dx + \frac{\varepsilon}{2} \int_{\Gamma_n} u^2 dx + \frac{1}{2} \int_{\Omega} t^2 |y(h)|^2 + 2t(y(u) - y_0)u(h) dx \\ &\quad + \frac{\varepsilon}{2} \int_{\Gamma_n} t^2 h^2 + 2thudx. \end{aligned}$$

Hence.

$$\frac{J(u + th) - J(u)}{t} = \int_{\Omega} (y(u) - y_0)u(h) dx + \varepsilon \int_{\Gamma_n} hudx + tK.$$

Where.

$$K = \frac{1}{2} \int_{\Omega} |y(h)|^2 dx + \frac{\varepsilon}{2} \int_{\Gamma_n} h^2 dx,$$

we then go to the limit and we make t tend towards 0. We then obtain the derivative of J :

$$J'(u, h) = \int_{\Omega} (y(u) - y_0)u(h)dx + \varepsilon \int_{\Gamma_n} hudx.$$

To solve the problem of the heat equation, we use the iterative gradient method :

$$u^{(n+1)} = u^{(n)} - \rho \nabla J(u) \quad \text{with} \quad \rho > 0,$$

we have :

$$J'(u, h) = \langle \nabla J(u), h \rangle = \int_{\Gamma_n} \nabla J(u)h.$$

1.2.2. Adjoint state method

To represent the gradient correctly, we need to transform \int_{Ω} into \int_{Γ_n} .

We use for that the method of the adjoint state : we therefore introduce the variable q verifying :

$$\begin{cases} -\Delta p = f & \text{in } \Omega, \\ p = ? & \text{on } \Gamma_d, \\ \frac{\partial p}{\partial n} = ? & \text{on } \Gamma_n, \end{cases}$$

one then rewrites the variational formulation and one determines the conditions at the edge of the field by comparing the variational formulation obtained with that of the initial problem.

$$\int_{\Omega} -\Delta p y(h) = \int_{\Omega} f y(h),$$

by Green's formula (twice) we have :

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{\Omega} \nabla p \nabla y(h) - \int_{\Gamma_n} \frac{\partial p}{\partial n} y(h) &= \int_{\Omega} f y(h) \\ \int_{\Omega} -p \Delta y(h) + \int_{\partial \Omega} (p \frac{\partial y(h)}{\partial n} - y(h) \frac{\partial p}{\partial n}) &= \int_{\Omega} f y(h) \\ \int_{\Gamma_n} p h + \int_{\Gamma_d} p \frac{\partial y(h)}{\partial n} - \int_{\Gamma_n} y(h) \frac{\partial p}{\partial n} &= \int_{\Omega} f y(h). \end{aligned}$$

The comparison with the initial problem then gives :

$$\begin{cases} -\Delta p = y(u) - y_0 & \text{in } \Omega, \\ p = 0 & \text{on } \Gamma_d, \\ \frac{\partial p}{\partial n} = 0 & \text{on } \Gamma_n, \end{cases}$$

we thus obtain :

$$\int_{\Gamma_n} p h = \int_{\Omega} (y(u) - y_0) y(h) \quad \text{where } p \text{ denotes the adjoint state.}$$

The derivative of Gâteaux is then defined in this case by :

$$J'(u, h) = \int_{\Gamma_n} \nabla J(u)h \quad \text{where} \quad \nabla J(u) = p + \varepsilon u.$$

1.2.3. Implementation of the algorithm

We give ourselves $u^{(0)} = 0$ (for example), then we solve for $i = 0, 1, \dots$ the direct problem, as well as the adjoint problem :

$$\begin{array}{cc} \text{Direct problem} & \text{Adjoint problem} \\ \left\{ \begin{array}{l} -\Delta y = 0, \\ y = 0, \\ \frac{\partial y}{\partial n} = u. \end{array} \right. & \left\{ \begin{array}{l} -\Delta p^{(i)} = y^{(i)} - u_0, \\ p^{(i)} = 0, \\ \frac{\partial p^{(i)}}{\partial n} = 0. \end{array} \right. \end{array}$$

The iterative gradient method gives us :

$$u^{(i+1)} = u^{(i)} - \rho \nabla J(u^{(i)}),$$

with,

$$\nabla J(u^{(i)}) = p^{(i)} + \varepsilon u^{(i)}.$$

1.3. The finite difference method

1.3.1. Laplace equation in dimension 2

One seeks to solve the problem numerically :

$$\begin{cases} -\Delta y = f & \text{in } \Omega =]0, 1[\times]0, 1[, \\ y = 0 & \text{on } \Gamma = \partial\Omega, \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

where $y = y(x, t)$, $\Delta = \partial_{xx}^2 + \partial_{tt}^2$ and $\partial\Omega$ is the edge of Ω .

We start by defining a mesh of Ω . We pose :

$$x_i = ih \quad \text{and} \quad t_n = nh,$$

where $0 \leq i, n \leq N + 1$, $h = \frac{1}{N+1}$ and $N \in \mathbb{N}$.

We will determine y_i^n approximating $y(x_i, t_n)$. By the Taylor development, we have :

$$\partial_{xx}^2 y(x_i, t_n) = \frac{y(x_{i+1}, t_n) - 2y(x_i, t_n) + y(x_{i-1}, t_n))}{h^2} + O(h^2),$$

and

$$\partial_{tt}^2 y(x_i, t_n) = \frac{y(x_i, t_{n+1}) - 2y(x_i, t_n) + y(x_i, t_{n-1}))}{h^2} + O(h^2).$$

A possible numerical scheme is then to consider the following approximation of $\Delta y(x_i, t_n)$.

$$\Delta_h y_i^n = \frac{-4y_i^n + y_{i+1}^n + y_{i-1}^n + y_i^{n+1} + y_i^{n-1}}{h^2}.$$

With this notation, the discretized problem is : find y_i^n such that :

$$\begin{cases} -\Delta_h y_i^n = f(x_i, t_n), & \text{for } 1 \leq i, n \leq N, \\ y_{0,n} = y_{N+1,n} = y_{i,0} = y_{i,N+1} = 0, & \text{for } 1 \leq i, n \leq N. \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

To write (4) in matrix form, we set

$$Y_h = (y_{11}, \dots, y_{1N}, y_{21}, \dots, y_{2N}, \dots, y_{NN})^T.$$

Then the problem (4) is written in the form

$$A_h Y_h = b_h,$$

where $A_h \in \mathbb{R}^{N^2 \times N^2}$ and $b_h \in \mathbb{R}^{N^2}$ are given by :

$$A_h = -\frac{1}{h^2} \begin{pmatrix} B & C & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ C & B & C & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & \ddots & \ddots & \ddots & 0 \\ \vdots & \ddots & \ddots & B & C \\ 0 & \dots & 0 & C & B \end{pmatrix},$$

$$b_h = \begin{pmatrix} f(x_1, y_1) \\ \vdots \\ f(x_1, y_N) \\ f(x_2, y_1) \\ \vdots \\ f(x_N, y_N) \end{pmatrix},$$

with,

$$B = \begin{pmatrix} -4 & 1 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 1 & -4 & 1 & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & \ddots & \ddots & \ddots & 0 \\ \vdots & \ddots & \ddots & -4 & 1 \\ 0 & \dots & 0 & 1 & -4 \end{pmatrix} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times N},$$

and $C = I_N \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times N}$.

The linear system being good, one can thus solve it.

Remark 1.1. We can choose a step h in x and another different step k for y . In that case, $A_h \in \mathbb{R}^{NM \times NM}$, where $h = \frac{1}{N+1}$ and $k = \frac{1}{M+1}$.

2. Application in optimal control

In this section, we will study practical problems of optimal control governed by differential partial differential equations. Within the framework of this work, we will deal with an optimal control problem applied to the heat equation.

This problem has many applications in physics and in automation.

Solving this problem is done by numerically calculating the optimal control by the finite difference method.

2.1. Optimal stationary control problem

2.1.1. Position of the problem

We consider our problem in an open domain Ω of \mathbb{R}^n ($n = 1, 2, 3$ in practice), with mixed Dirichlet and Neumann conditions at the edge of this domain.

Denote by $\partial\Omega = \Gamma_d \cup \Gamma_n$ the boundary of the domain.

The problem to be solved is the equation of stationary heat (not time dependent).

$$\begin{cases} -\Delta y &= 0 & \text{in } \Omega, \\ y &= 0 & \text{on } \Gamma_d, \\ \frac{\partial y}{\partial n} &= u & \text{on } \Gamma_n, \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

with $y = y(u)$ and $u = u(x)$, where y denotes the temperature and u controls it.

Our aim is then to find the temperature y such that it is equal to a given temperature y_0 , or at least very close to it.

To do this, we define the following cost functional J :

$$J(u) = \frac{1}{2} \int_{\Omega} |y(u) - y_0|^2 + \frac{\varepsilon}{2} \int_{\Gamma_n} u^2, \quad (6)$$

where ε represents the efficiency-cost trade-off.

The functional (6) must be minimized, and denote by u its unique minimum

$$\min J(u) \quad \text{such that} \quad u \in L^2(\Gamma_n).$$

The problem (5) amounts to finding $y \in H_0^1(\Gamma_d)$ such that :

$$\int_{\Omega} -\Delta y v = 0, \quad \forall v \in H_0^1(\Gamma_d).$$

According to Green's formula, we have :

$$\int_{\Omega} \nabla y \nabla v - \int_{\Gamma_n} \frac{\partial y}{\partial n} v = 0.$$

We then get :

$$\int_{\Omega} \nabla y \nabla v = \int_{\Gamma_n} u v.$$

We have $V_h \subset H_0^1(\Gamma_d)$ of finite dimension.

We assume the finite dimensional problem and in the following, we will continue to denote by V and H the finite dimensional subspaces of $H_0^1(\Gamma_d)$ and $L^2(\Gamma_n)$.

On the other hand, to minimize the functional J , it is first necessary to perform the derivation operation on it. For this, we introduce the directional derivative defined as follows

$$J'(u, h) = \lim_{t \rightarrow 0} \frac{J(u + th) - J(u)}{t}.$$

Indeed, we have

$$J(u + th) = \frac{1}{2} \int_{\Omega} |y(u + th) - y_0|^2 + \frac{\varepsilon}{2} \int_{\Gamma_n} (u + th)^2.$$

As the map $u \mapsto y(u)$ is linear, we have $y(u + th) = y(u) + ty(h)$. So we get

$$\begin{aligned} J(u + th) &= \frac{1}{2} \int_{\Omega} |y(u) - y_0 + ty(h)|^2 + \frac{\varepsilon}{2} \int_{\Gamma_n} (u^2 + t^2 h^2 + 2thu) \\ &= \frac{1}{2} \int_{\Omega} |y(u) - y_0|^2 + t^2 |y(h)|^2 \\ &\quad + 2t(y(u) - y_0)y(h) + \frac{\varepsilon}{2} \int_{\Gamma_n} (u^2 + t^2 h^2 + 2thu). \end{aligned}$$

Hence.

$$\frac{J(u + th) - J(u)}{t} = \int_{\Omega} (y(u) - y_0)y(h) + \varepsilon \int_{\Gamma_n} uh + Kt,$$

where,

$$K = \frac{1}{2} \int_{\Omega} |y(h)|^2 + \frac{\varepsilon}{2} \int_{\Gamma_n} h^2.$$

By passing to the limit when t tends towards 0, we then obtain the derivative of J :

$$J'(u, h) = \int_{\Omega} (y(u) - y_0)y(h) + \varepsilon \int_{\Gamma_n} uh.$$

The resolution of this control problem by the iterative gradient method is done according to the following iteration :

$$u^{(n+1)} = u^{(n)} - \rho \nabla J(u^{(n)}),$$

where $\rho > 0$.

We then have

$$J'(u, h) = \langle \nabla J(u), h \rangle = \int_{\Gamma_n} \nabla J(u)h.$$

2.1.2. Adjoint state method

So that the gradient is well represented, it is necessary to transform the integral on Ω towards the integral on Γ_n . For that, we use the method of the state adjoint, by introducing the variable p verifying

$$\begin{cases} -\Delta p &= f & \text{in } \Omega, \\ p &= \alpha & \text{on } \Gamma_d, \\ \frac{\partial p}{\partial n} &= \beta & \text{on } \Gamma_n. \end{cases} \quad (7)$$

Now, one will determine the conditions at the edge of the field, by rewriting the variational formulation of the problem, and by comparing with the conditions at the edge of the initial problem. Indeed, we have :

$$- \int_{\Omega} \Delta p y(h) = \int_{\Omega} f y(h).$$

By integration by parts, we successively obtain :

$$\begin{aligned} \int_{\Omega} f y(h) &= \int_{\Omega} \nabla p \nabla y(h) - \int_{\partial\Omega} \frac{\partial p}{\partial n} y(h) \\ &= - \int_{\Omega} p \Delta y(h) + \int_{\partial\Omega} \left(p \frac{\partial y(h)}{\partial n} - y(h) \frac{\partial p}{\partial n} \right) \\ &= \int_{\Gamma_n} p h + \int_{\Gamma_d} p \frac{\partial y(h)}{\partial n} - \int_{\Gamma_n} y(h) \frac{\partial p}{\partial n}. \end{aligned}$$

The comparison with the problem (5) gives us

$$\begin{cases} -\Delta p = y(u) - y_0 & \text{in } \Omega, \\ p = 0 & \text{on } \Gamma_d, \\ \frac{\partial p}{\partial n} = 0 & \text{on } \Gamma_n. \end{cases} \quad (8)$$

We thus obtain :

$$\int_{\Gamma_n} p h = \int_{\Omega} (y(u) - y_0) y(h),$$

where p denotes the adjoint state.

The directional derivative of the functional J is then defined by :

$$J'(u, h) = \int_{\Gamma_n} \nabla J(u) h, \quad \text{where } \nabla J(u) = p + \varepsilon u. \quad (9)$$

2.1.3. Solving algorithm

We give ourselves an initial value $u^{(0)}$, then we solve the direct problem and the adjoint problem for $i = 0, 1, \dots$

$$\begin{aligned} &\text{Direct problem} \\ \begin{cases} -\Delta y^{(i)} = 0 & \text{in } \Omega, \\ y^{(i)} = 0 & \text{on } \Gamma_d, \\ \frac{\partial y^{(i)}}{\partial n} = u^{(i)} & \text{on } \Gamma_n. \end{cases} \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\text{Adjoint problem} \\ \begin{cases} -\Delta p^{(i)} = y^{(i)} - y_0 & \text{in } \Omega, \\ p^{(i)} = 0 & \text{on } \Gamma_d, \\ \frac{\partial p^{(i)}}{\partial n} = 0 & \text{on } \Gamma_n. \end{cases} \end{aligned}$$

The iterative gradient method gives us

$$u^{(i+1)} = u^i - \rho \nabla J(u^i), \quad \text{with } \nabla J(u^i) = p^{(i)} + \varepsilon u^i.$$

2.1.4. Example of application

We consider in dimension 1 the following problem :

$$\begin{cases} -y'' = f & \text{in } \Omega, \\ y(1) = b & \text{on } \Gamma_d, \\ y'(0) = a & \text{on } \Gamma_n, \end{cases}$$

where $f(x) = \pi^2 \cos(\pi x)$, $\Omega = (]0, 1[)$, $\Gamma_d = \{1\}$, $a = 0$ and $b = -1$.

Step 1 : We subdivide the domain into N parts, and we solve the problem at the point $x_i = (i - 1)h$, where h denotes the step of the subdivision with $h = \frac{1}{N}$.

We can discretize the previous problem by using the finite difference method

$$y''(x_i) = \frac{y_{i-1} - 2y_i + y_{i+1}}{h^2}, \text{ where } y_i = y(x_i).$$

We obtain,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{y_{i-1} - 2y_i + y_{i+1}}{h^2} &= -f(x_i), & 2 \leq i \leq N - 1, \\ \frac{-y_i + y_{i+1}}{h^2} &= -f(x_i) + \frac{a}{h}, & i = 1, \\ \frac{y_{i-1} - 2y_i}{h^2} &= -f(x_i) - \frac{b}{h^2}, & i = N. \end{aligned}$$

The problem thus amounts to solving the linear system $AY = F$, where

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} -1 & 1 & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ 1 & -2 & 1 & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & \ddots & \ddots & \ddots & 0 \\ \vdots & \ddots & \ddots & -2 & 1 \\ 0 & \cdots & 0 & 1 & -2 \end{pmatrix},$$

$$Y = \begin{pmatrix} y_1 \\ \cdot \\ \cdot \\ \cdot \\ y_N \end{pmatrix},$$

and

$$F = h^2 \begin{pmatrix} -f(x_1) + \frac{a}{h} \\ -f(x_2) \\ \cdot \\ \cdot \\ -f(x_N) - \frac{b}{h^2} \end{pmatrix}.$$

Solving the linear system gives us a vector Y with N components.

Step 2 : After this step, by the same method we solve the adjoint problem :

$$\begin{cases} -p'' &= y - y_0 & \text{in } \Omega, \\ p(1) &= 0 & \text{on } \Gamma_d, \\ p'(0) &= 0 & \text{on } \Gamma_n. \end{cases}$$

The finite difference method allows to write

$$p''(x_i) = \frac{p_{i-1} - 2p_i + p_{i+1}}{h^2}, \text{ where } p_i = p(x_i),$$

We obtain,

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{p_{i-1} - 2p_i + p_{i+1}}{h^2} &= -y_i + y_0, & 2 \leq i \leq N - 1, \\ \frac{-p_i + p_{i+1}}{h^2} &= -y_i + y_0, & i = 1, \\ \frac{p_{i-1} - 2p_i}{h^2} &= -y_i + y_0, & i = N. \end{aligned}$$

The linear system obtained is $AP = G$, where

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} -1 & 1 & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ 1 & -2 & 1 & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & \ddots & \ddots & \ddots & 0 \\ \vdots & \ddots & \ddots & -2 & 1 \\ 0 & \cdots & 0 & 1 & -2 \end{pmatrix},$$

$$P = \begin{pmatrix} p_1 \\ \vdots \\ p_N \end{pmatrix},$$

and

$$G = h^2 \begin{pmatrix} -y_1 + y_0 \\ -y_2 + y_0 \\ \vdots \\ -y_N + y_0 \end{pmatrix}.$$

Step 3 : The previous step allowed to calculate the solution p of the adjoint problem, then we calculate

$$\nabla J(u^{(i)}) = p^{(i)} + \varepsilon u^{(i)},$$

and

$$u^{(i+1)} = u^{(i)} - \rho \nabla J(u^{(i)}), \quad \text{where } u^{(0)} = a.$$

One fixes an error precision and one stops computations.

2.2. Optimal non-stationary control problem

Let the heat equation, therefore the temperature y depends on two variables $y = y(x, t)$, with $x \in \Omega =]0, 1[$ and $t \in]0, T[, T > 0$.

The problem to be solved is as follows :

$$\begin{cases} \frac{\partial y}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial^2 y}{\partial x^2} = \zeta(x, t) & \text{in } \mathcal{Q} =]0, 1[\times]0, T[, \\ y(0) = y^0 & \text{in } \Omega, \\ y = u(t) & \text{on } \Sigma = \Gamma \times]0, T[, \end{cases} \quad (11)$$

where Γ is the border of Ω , y^0 is the initial state, $\zeta \in L^2(\mathcal{Q})$ and $u \in L^2(]0, T[)$.

The functional to be minimized is given by :

$$J(u) = \frac{1}{2} \int_0^T \int_0^1 |y(u) - y_0|^2 dxdt + \frac{\varepsilon}{2} \int_0^T u^2(t) dt, \quad (12)$$

and the directional derivative of the functional (12) is equal to

$$J'(u, h) = \int_0^T \int_0^1 (y(u) - y_0) y(h) dxdt + \varepsilon \int_0^T u h dt,$$

with y_0 is the measured (or given) state.

2.2.1. Adjoint state method

In the same way as for the stationary problem (7), we define $p = p(x, t)$ solution of :

$$\begin{cases} -\frac{\partial p}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial^2 p}{\partial x^2} = y(x, t; u) - y_0 & \text{in } \mathcal{Q}, \\ p(T) = 0 & \text{in } \Omega, \\ p = 0 & \text{on } \Sigma, \end{cases} \quad (13)$$

If we set $\hat{p}(x, t) = p(x, T - t)$, our adjoint problem is then written

$$\begin{cases} -\frac{\partial p}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial^2 p}{\partial x^2} = y(x, T - t; u) - y_0 & \text{in } \mathcal{Q}, \\ p(0) = 0 & \text{in } \Omega, \\ p = 0 & \text{on } \Sigma, \end{cases} \quad (14)$$

2.2.2. Solving algorithm

The method of solving the nonstationary problem is the same as that of the stationary problem, it therefore consists in solving the direct problem as well as the adjoint problem

$$\begin{array}{c} \text{Direct problem} \\ \left\{ \begin{array}{l} \frac{\partial y_i^n}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial^2 y_i^n}{\partial x^2} = \zeta_i^n \quad \text{in } \mathcal{Q}, \\ y_i(t_0) = y_i^0 \quad \text{in } \Omega, \\ y_N^n, y_0^n = 0 \quad \text{on }]0, T[, \end{array} \right. \end{array} \quad (15)$$

$$\begin{array}{c} \text{Adjoint problem} \\ \left\{ \begin{array}{l} -\frac{\partial p_i^n}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial^2 p_i^n}{\partial x^2} = y_i^n(x, T - t; u) - y_0 \quad \text{in } \mathcal{Q}, \\ p_i^0 = 0 \quad \text{in } \Omega, \\ p_N^n, p_0^n = 0 \quad \text{on }]0, T[, \end{array} \right. \end{array} \quad (16)$$

2.2.3. Example of application

We consider in dimension 1 the following problem with the control on the edge :

$$\begin{cases} \frac{\partial y}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial^2 y}{\partial x^2} = (1 + \pi^2 t) \sin(\pi x) & \text{in } \mathcal{Q}, \\ y(x, 0) = 0 & \text{in } \Omega, \\ y(0, t) = \pi t & \text{on }]0, T[, \\ y(1, t) = 0 & \text{on }]0, T[. \end{cases} \quad (17)$$

Step 1 : We define the decomposition steps of space and time

$x_i = (i - 1)h$ and $t_n = n\tau$, with $h = \frac{1}{N-1}$ and $\tau = \frac{T}{k}$ for $i = \overline{1, N}$ and $n = \overline{0, k}$.

The discretization of the problem in space and in time for an implicit diagram, gives us

$$\frac{\partial^2 y}{\partial x^2}(x_i, t_n) \simeq \frac{y_{i-1}^n - 2y_i^n + y_{i+1}^n}{h^2},$$

and

$$\frac{\partial y}{\partial t} \simeq \frac{y_i^n - y_i^{n-1}}{\tau},$$

where $y_i^n = y(x_i, t_n)$.

We obtain :

$$\frac{y_i^n - y_i^{n-1}}{\tau} - \frac{y_{i-1}^n - 2y_i^n + y_{i+1}^n}{h^2} = (1 + \pi^2 t_n) \sin(\pi x_i), \text{ for } 2 \leq i \leq N - 1,$$

With $y_i^0 = 0$ for $i = \overline{1, N}$,

$y_1^n = \pi t_n$ for $n = \overline{0, k}$,

$y_N^n = 0$ for $n = \overline{0, k}$.

So the problem can be written in the following matrix form :

$$\frac{1}{\tau} Y^n - \frac{1}{\tau} Y^{n-1} - \frac{1}{h^2} A Y^n = F^n,$$

where

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} -2 & 1 & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ 1 & -2 & 1 & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & \ddots & \ddots & \ddots & 0 \\ \vdots & \ddots & \ddots & -2 & 1 \\ 0 & \cdots & 0 & 1 & -2 \end{pmatrix},$$

$$Y^n = \begin{pmatrix} y_1^n \\ \vdots \\ y_N^n \end{pmatrix},$$

and

$$F^n = \begin{pmatrix} (1 + \pi^2 t_n) \sin(\pi x_1) - \pi t_n \\ \vdots \\ (1 + \pi^2 t_n) \sin(\pi x_N) \end{pmatrix}.$$

The matrix system can still be written in the form

$$\left(\frac{1}{\tau} I - \frac{1}{h^2} A \right) Y^n = F^n + \frac{1}{\tau} Y^{n-1}, \text{ where } I \text{ is the unit matrix.}$$

Step 2 : The previous step gives us the solution of the direct problem, so the second member of the adjoint problem is calculated. By the same method, we will solve the latter

$$\begin{cases} -\frac{\partial p}{\partial t} - \frac{\partial^2 p}{\partial x^2} = y(x, T - t; u) - y_0 & \text{in } \mathcal{Q}, \\ p(0) = 0 & \text{in } \Omega, \\ p(0, t) = 0 & \text{on }]0, T[, \\ p(1, t) = 0 & \text{on }]0, T[, \end{cases}$$

with

$$\frac{\partial^2 p}{\partial x^2}(x_i, t_n) \simeq \frac{p_{i-1}^n - 2p_i^n + p_{i+1}^n}{h^2},$$

and

$$\frac{\partial p}{\partial t} \simeq \frac{p_i^n - p_i^{n-1}}{\tau},$$

where $p_i^n = p(x_i, t_n)$.

We obtain

$$\frac{p_i^n - p_i^{n-1}}{\tau} - \frac{p_{i-1}^n - 2p_i^n + p_{i+1}^n}{h^2} = y(x_i, T - t_n) - y_0, \text{ for } 2 \leq i \leq N - 1,$$

With $p_i^0 = 0$ for $i = \overline{1, N}$,

$p_1^n = 0$ for $n = \overline{0, k}$,

$p_N^n = 0$ for $n = \overline{0, k}$.

So the problem can be written in the following matrix form :

$$\frac{1}{\tau} P^n - \frac{1}{\tau} P^{n-1} - \frac{1}{h^2} A P^n = G^n,$$

where

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} -2 & 1 & 0 & \cdots & 0 \\ 1 & -2 & 1 & \ddots & \vdots \\ 0 & \ddots & \ddots & \ddots & 0 \\ \vdots & \ddots & \ddots & -2 & 1 \\ 0 & \cdots & 0 & 1 & -2 \end{pmatrix},$$

$$P^n = \begin{pmatrix} p_1^n \\ \vdots \\ \vdots \\ p_N^n \end{pmatrix},$$

and

$$G^n = \begin{pmatrix} y(x_1, T - t_n) - y_0 \\ \vdots \\ \vdots \\ y(x_N, T - t_n) - y_0 \end{pmatrix}.$$

The matrix system can still write in the form :

$$\left(\frac{1}{\tau} I - \frac{1}{h^2} A \right) P^n = G^n + \frac{1}{\tau} P^{n-1}, \text{ where } I \text{ is the unit matrix.}$$

Step 3 : Once the two direct and adjoint problems are solved, we then calculate in this step the next approximation of the control

$$\nabla J(u^{(i)}) = p^{(i)}(0, T - t) + \varepsilon u^{(i)}(t),$$

and

$$u^{(i+1)}(t) = u^{(i)}(t) - \rho \nabla J(u^{(i)}), \quad \text{where } u^{(0)}(t) = \pi t.$$

3. Conclusion

Our contribution in this work is the numerical analysis of differential equations with partial derivatives, and the application of the latter in optimal control.

For this, in the first section, we present the general principle of the finite difference method in dimension greater than or equal to one to calculate the approximate solution of an PDE.

In the second section, we discussed the application of this method on two practical applications in optimal control, the first application relates to a stationary problem and the second on the nonstationary case.

Acknowledgements

The authors thank the referee for his helpful comments and suggestions.

This work was supported by the Directorate-General for Scientific Research and Technological Development (DGRSDT).

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